

INTEGRATED OPTIMUM DESIGN OF WING STRUCTURE WITH COMPOSITE SKINS

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SUMMARY: A minimum weight design procedure of wing structure with composite skins is described briefly, in which strength, frequency, displacement, divergence velocity, control-surface efficiency, flutter speed and thickness are considered as constraints. Main methods used in the procedure are also presented. New engineering requirements are imposed upon the integrated optimization design of composite structure. Method to meet these requirements are suggested and implemented in a newly developed Composite Structure Analysis and Optimum Design Program System (COMPASS). By using the automated design tool, the integrated optimization design for a delta wing structure with composite skins was performed. Under the constraints of unidirectional strains, total thickness limit, balanced-symmetrical limit and flutter speed, the optimum thickness of each ply orientation has been obtained. From the full-scale tests of the wing for strength, durability and damage tolerance, and the tests of ground resonance oscillation and flight of the airplane, it is indicated that tests values are in good compliance with the optimization design results and the integrated optimum design procedure and methods described in this paper can be used for practical optimization design of wing structure with composite skins

KEYWORDS: optimization, constraint, variable, integrate, structure design, composite skin

INTRODUCTION

Generally speaking, a weight saving of over 20% could be achieved when metallic skins of aircraft wing structure are replaced by advanced composite material skins. In addition, by using the characteristics of directional stiffness and the coupling effects of bending and twisting of composite, beneficial aeroelastic deformation (static or dynamic) of wing structure can be obtained. The integrated optimum design technique is a supporting technique to acquire minimum weight of aircraft structure and improve its aeroelastic performances. When composite materials are used on skins of wing structure, they bring new requirements to the technique. In this paper, a integrated optimization design procedure and methods used in the design of a delta wing structure with composite skins are described. New engineering requirements encountered during the optimization design procedure, such as how to find the maximum design point for composite laminate controlled by unidirectional strains, balanced-symmetrical limit and total thickness limit, are discussed. Methods to meet these requirements are also proposed. Test results indicate that the integrated optimum design procedure and methods used for the wing structure are very effective and efficient.

PROCEDURE AND METHODS

Procedure

The flow chart of the optimization design procedure for wing structures is shown in Fig 1.

Fig. 1: Procedure of integrated optimum design for wing structures

Methods

Structure Response Analysis

The displacement methods are used to solve the force balance equation:

$$[k] \{u\} = \{F\} \quad (1)$$

where $[k]$ is the stiffness matrix, $\{u\}$ is the displacement vector and $\{F\}$ is the force vector.

Inherent characteristic problems can be reduced to solve the eigenvalues of the flowing equation:

$$[c] [M] \{q\} = (1 / \lambda) \{q\} \quad (2)$$

where $[c]$ is the damping matrix, $[M]$ is the generalized mass matrix, $\{q\}$ is the generalized mode shape and λ is the eigenvalue.

Flutter analysis includes the calculation of unsteady aerodynamic loads and the solving of flutter equation.

The Subsonic Doublet - Lattice Lifting Surface Method is used to calculate the unsteady aerodynamic loads and the v-g method used to calculate the flutter speed:

$$\lambda \{q\} = ([M_{mn}] + (1/k)[A_{mn}])^{-1} [\omega_m^2 M_{mn}] \{q\} \quad (3)$$

where λ is the eigenvalue, $\{q\}$ is the complex characteristic vector and $[M_{mn}]$ is the generalized mass matrix, ω_m is the frequency, $1/k$ is the reduced frequency and $[A_{mn}]$ is the matrix related to the structure^[4].

Static aeroelasticity analysis

Kernel Function Method is used to calculate the coefficients of aerodynamic loads, and the equations to calculate the divergence speed is:

$$V_D = \sqrt{\frac{2q_D}{\rho}} \quad (4)$$

where ρ is the air density and q_D is the eigenvalue of the following function

$$([K_{EE}] - q[R_{EE}])\{\xi_{EE}\} = \{0\} \quad (5)$$

where $[K_{EE}]$ is the generalized stiffness matrix and $[R_{EE}]$ is the generalized aerodynamic loads matrix.

Control-surface efficiency calculating equation is^[4]

$$m_{x^{\prime\prime}} = s^{-1} \ell^{-1} \left\{ \left[\bar{z} \right] \{q\} + q \left[\bar{z} \right]^B \phi \cdot (\bar{K} - q \bar{R})^{-1} \phi \{q\}^T \right\} \quad (6)$$

Constraint Considerations

When designing a wing structure, the constraint conditions, such as dimension, stress, strain, displacement, vibration frequency, control-surface efficiency, divergence velocity and flutter speed, must be considered. To make the numerical value of constraint equation stable and speed up the convergence, constraint screening and norming techniques are used^[4].

Sensitivity Analysis

The sensitivity analysis take the longest time during the integrated optimum calculation. To reduce the computing time, the analytical derivative method is used as a primary method supported by the difference method. As the static aeroelastic analysis are based on the structure mode shapes, it is able to calculate the static aeroelastic sensitivity of large FEM.

Approximate Treatment

The goal of approximation treatment is to reduce structure re-analysis times and the dimension number of design variables and to increase the computing efficiency. The following approximation techniques are used:

Variable block, key element and variable linking method to reduce the variable numbers.

Temporal deletion of some constraints which can not become critical constraints when the variables are properly changed, to reduce constraint number during optimization calculation.

First-order Taylor-series expansion as explicit approximation expressions of the object and constraint functions, to reduce structure re-analysis times.

Limit the modified value of variables properly in every optimization step, to confirm the optimum searching in an adequate precision range and to improve the convergence performance.

Optimum Design Model

The structure weight, stress, strain, displacement, vibration frequency, control-surface efficiency, divergence velocity and flutter speed are defined as structure responses, one response or a combination of some response as the objective functions and the other repossess as the design constraints and the structural element sizes are selected as the design variables. For example, when we define weight as objective function, the optimum model can be reduced to the following mathematical programming problem:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{find } = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\} & (7) \\
 & \text{min. } f(x) \\
 & \text{s.t } \mathbf{g}_j(x) \leq 0 & j = 1, 2, \dots, M \\
 & x_i^l \leq x_i \leq x_i^u & i = 1, 2, \dots, N
 \end{aligned}$$

where M is the number of constraints and N is the number of variables.

Optimization Design Algorithm

The Sequential Unconstrained Mathematical Techniques (SUMT) is used to obtain the minimum weight, in the following steps:

Conversion of the constrained problems to unconstrained minimization problems; solving the unconstrained problem with the Modified Newton Method;

Using Golden Section Method to solve one-dimension minimum search, and obtain the optimum step.

ENGINEERING REQUIREMENTS FOR THE INTEGRATED OPTIMUM DESIGN OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

Maximum Design Point

When composite materials are used on wing skins, the strength constraints are unidirectional strains required by durability and damage tolerance. Constraint space limited by the curved line (strength criterion of the curved line is often used by the academic environment) is different from that limited by the unidirectional constraints(Fig. 2). The requirement is how to find the maximum design point A for a composite laminate controlled by multi-unidirectional strains.

We apply the unidirectional constraints simultaneously to a composite key element controlled by static strength to find the optimum design point A.

Fig. 2: Constraint space of composite lams controlled by strength

Balanced-Symmetrical Limit

Although the coupling characteristics of a laminate are needed for aeroelastic tailoring designs of composite wing structures, in some cases the balanced-symmetrical laminates are required to reduce deformation of the laminates during curing process, so the balanced - symmetrical design requirement is made.

We take the following steps to meet the balanced-symmetrical requirements
 adds the sensitivities of the variables which are required to be balanced or symmetrical

$$\partial \Pi / \partial D_{+\theta} + \partial \Pi / \partial D_{-\theta} = \partial \Pi / \partial D_{\pm\theta} \quad (8)$$

re-assigning their sensitivity values before iteration

$$\partial \Pi / \partial D_{+\theta} = \partial \Pi / \partial D_{-\theta} = \frac{1}{2} \partial \Pi / \partial D_{\pm\theta} \quad (9)$$

Total Thickness Limit

Consider a laminate composed of n ply orientations and the thickness of each ply orientation is taken as a variable(see Fig. 3). For some cases in practical designs, the total thickness dimension D is limited. Usually engineers choose D/n as the upper limit for each variable to meet the total thickness limit. As the weight sensitivity to the active constraint of each variable differ widely (because the orientation of each ply are different), such a case can probably happen that the variable having the maximum sensitivity reaches its upper limit and is limited, while the others do not reach their upper limits. If this occasion happens, the design results can not be a optimized one obviously. So a method to treat this special case is required.

$$d_i^u = \frac{\partial \Pi / w_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k \partial \Pi / \partial w_i} (D - \sum_{j=1}^{n-k} d_j^l) \quad (10)$$

where d_i^u is the upper limit of variable d_i , $\frac{\partial \Pi / \partial w_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k \partial \Pi / \partial w_i}$ is the weight sensitivity percentage of variable d_i , k is the number of variables which have positive sensitivities and $\sum_{j=1}^{n-k} d_j^l$ is the sum of the lower limit of variables which have negative sensitivities.

Fig. 3: Plot to explain the total thickness dimension limit

APPLICATION EXAMPLE

Using the integrated optimum design computer program (COMPASS) based on the procedure and methods mentioned above, the integrated optimum design for the composite skins of a delta wing structure carrying a external tank was performed. This wing structure has metallic ribs and beams, its FEM is shown in Fig. 4 and the location of composite skins are shown in Fig. 5. The composite skins were partitioned into 12 variable blocks, 12 key elements and 48 variables (thickness) and two cases of critical load are taken into consideration. The design goals are to obtain the minimum structure weight and an increased flutter speed. The constraints are shown in table 1.

Fig. 4 FEM of the wing structure carrying a external tank

Fig. 5 The location of composite skins and variable blocks

Table 1: Integrated optimum design constraints

Items	Constraints
Allowable Tension Strain (a.t.s)	3500 ($\mu\epsilon$)
Allowable Compression Strain(a.c.s)	2700 ($\mu\epsilon$)
Allowable Shear Strain (a.s.s)	5300 ($\mu\epsilon$)
Balanced and Symmetrical	Thickness at $+45^0$ equals to that at -45^0
Total Thickness	Total thickness D less than 5(mm) for block 11, and less than 6(mm) for the other blocks
Flutter Speed	276.00 (m/s)

After 6 iteration steps, the optimization calculation was converged and all constraints were satisfied. Fig. 6 shows the strain ratios of tension and shear of a key element controlled by static strength and indicate that two unidirectional strain ratios converge toward the optimum value 1. Fig. 7 shows the iteration process of variable thickness, in which the $+45^0$ -ply thickness is equal to the 45^0 -ply and the balanced-symmetrical constraint satisfied. Fig. 8 shows the flutter speed versus incremental structure weight, in which the average sensitivity criterion is applied to line 1. The technique makes the upper limit of a variable higher if it's sensitivity is higher. As the thickness distribution to each ply orientation in the laminate is more reasonable under the constraint of the total thickness, the structure weight efficiency is increased.

The convergence tendency of flutter and structure weight is typical (Fig. 9 and Fig. 10). As a large external tank is taken into account, the coupling between the store pitch and the first wing bending results in a slow flutter type. The flutter v-g plot is shown in Fig. 11. Table 2 is the results of the integrated optimum design.

Fig. 6: Strain ratios of tension and shear

Fig. 7: Variable thickness history of iteration

Fig. 8: Flutter speed vs. incremental structure weight

Fig. 9 Structure weight history of iteration

Fig. 10: The flutter speed history of iteration

Fig. 11 Plot of v-g

Table 2: Results of integrated optimum design

Block No	Ply layout (angle _{ply number})	Active Constraint Type	Block No	Ply layout (angle _{ply number})	Active Constraint Type
1	0 ₈ /±45 ₂₈ /90 ₃	strength	7	0 ₈ /±45 ₁₆ /90 ₃	strength
2	0 ₈ /±45 ₂₄ /90 ₃	strength	8	0 ₈ /±45 ₂₄ /90 ₃	flutter
3	0 ₈ /±45 ₁₆ /90 ₅	strength	9	0 ₈ /±45 ₁₂ /90 ₂	strength
4	0 ₁₂ /±45 ₂₈ /90 ₃	flutter	10	0 ₁₀ /±45 ₁₂ /90 ₄	strength
5	0 ₈ /±45 ₂₄ /90 ₃	strength	11	0 ₁₁ /±45 ₂₈ /90 ₄	flutter
6	0 ₁₀ /±45 ₃₆ /90 ₅	flutter	12	0 ₇ /±45 ₁₂ /90 ₂	flutter
1. The total weight saving of composite skins is 20%.					
2. The flutter speed of the composite wing with an 1400(L) external tank is increased by 23% compared with the metallic wing.					

TEST RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

To verify the integrated optimum design results of Table 2, three full-scale wing structures with composite skins are fabricated, one for static strength, durability and damage tolerance tests, the other two for ground resonance oscillation and flight tests. The results indicate that the test values are in good compliance with the optimization design results of Table 2^[2].

CONCLUSION

The integrated optimum design procedure and methods described in this paper can be used for the practical optimization design of wing structures with composite skins, the engineering requirements can be satisfied and the design results are verified by a lot of different types of tests.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Xu Yang, 'Research of Integrated Optimum design for Composite wing structure', Technical Report of Shenyang Aircraft Company, 1993.5.
- [2]. Yining Zhang, 'Research and Manufacturing Summarization of Composite Wing Structure with Integrated Full Tanks', Technical Report of Shenyang Aircraft Company, 1995.11.
- [3]. Yining Zhang, 'Theoretical Manual of SAFDOP', Technical Report of Shenyang Aircraft Company, 1985.10.
- [4]. Huiliang Ding, 'Theoretical Manual of COMPASS', Technical Report of Airplane Strength Research Institute, P.R. China , 1989.3.
- [5]. D.J.Neill, 'ASTPOS-A Multidisciplinary Automated Structural Design Tool', N89-25174.
- [6]. CLINTON V.ECKSTROM, CHARLES V., 'Design Considerations And Experiences in The Use of Composite Material For An Aeroelastic Research Wing', NASA Technical Memorandum 83291.
- [7]. Michael H.shirk, Terrence J.Hertz, 'Aeroelastic Tailoring - Theory, Practice,-and Promise', J.AIRCRAFT, Vol.23, No.1.
- [8]. Warner L, Edwin Lerner, 'Application of Structural Optimization for Strength and Aeroelastic Design Requirements', AGARD R-664.
- [9]. V.B.Venkayya, 'Recent Developments in Large-Scale Structural Optimization', N89-25231.
- [10]. K.B.Bowman, 'Optimum Structural Design With Static Aeroelastic Constraints', N89-25171.
- [11]. Philip Mason, 'Applications of Integrated Design /Analysis Systems in Aerospace Structural Design', N89-25147.